

THE CONCEPT AND FEATURES OF BIG DATA

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Abstract

It is no coincidence that information today is perceived as a new resource, or, one might even say, a new factor of production, due to the change in values, in relation to which there is interest from subjects in the digital economy. At the same time, the actual increase in the volume of information, due to the emergence of an increasing number of information sources, leads to a situation where “manual” methods and methods for collecting and processing a set of information lose their relevance, being replaced by highly intelligent computer technologies, and traditional information storage databases are online. -servers.

All these interdependent processes have given rise to a new phenomenon of the information ecosystem – “Big Data”, which has become an integral part of the civil law turnover. Surely, the emergence of such a digital object has affected all spheres of society, not bypassing, among other things, law. In this regard, the relevance of the presented study for the legal world is extremely vital.

Keywords: *Big Data, database, digital asset, data mining, artificial intelligence, volume, veracity, velocity, data value, variety.*

Introduction

Big Data is a relatively new phenomenon for the modern world, and therefore it is possible to establish the source of the appearance of this term. In the scientific literature, the introduction of the concept of “Big Data” into wide use is associated with its use by Clifford Lynch in the British scientific journal *Nature*, published on September 3, 2008², where, among other things, the significance of the emerging new paradigm was discussed. However, several scientific papers

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² Lynch, C. How do your data grow?. *Nature* 455, 28–29 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1038/455028a>

used this term long before describing the features, methods and ways of analyzing Big Data.³ Big Data is gaining momentum in popularity every year, attracting the attention of many scientists. By 2011, Microsoft and IBM began to use Big Data in their projects, which further fueled interest in the new phenomenon. By 2013, universities began to introduce “Big Data” as a separate subject, which once again emphasizes the need to study the emerging phenomenon.

The concept of Big Data

The rapid spread of Big Data undoubtedly makes us think about the need to develop not only technical methods of regulation, but also about the legal aspects of regulation. Unfortunately, the legal form does not always keep pace with the information environment. The improvement of Big Data is no exception of it. Due to the complexity of the procedure for modifying the legal system, formalism in the legal regulation of the sphere under consideration should be avoided. Therefore, at the first stage of developing the regulatory framework for a new phenomenon, it is necessary to create a “framework” legal structures that would establish a general regulation procedure (concepts, principles, etc.) for flexible adaptation to constant changes in the innovation sphere, and would become the basis for creating sectorial legislation in future. Therefore, first, it would be necessary to develop basic legal concepts, which leads to the need to determine the nature of Big Data. Similar ideas could be found in V. A. Vaypan, who divides the development of the digital economy into stages, where the initial one was the formation of fundamental legal concepts and institutions⁴. In the literature, attempts have been repeatedly made to formulate a definition of Big Data, however, there is lack of unified approach to the concept under

³ John R. Mashey. Big Data and the Next Wave of InfraStress. 1998. URL: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/1999-usenix-annual-technical-conference/big-data-and-next-wave-infrastress-problems>; Michael Cox. David Ellsworth. Application-controlled demand paging for out-of-core visualization // Proceedings of the IEEE 8th conference on Visualization. October 1997. URL: <https://www.nas.nasa.gov/assets/pdf/techreports/1997/nas-97-010.pdf>; Lyman, Peter, Hal R. Varian. "How Much Information". 2003. URL: <http://groups.ischool.berkeley.edu/archive/how-much-info-2003/>

⁴ Vaypan, V. A. (2017). Fundamentals of legal regulation of the digital economy. Law and economics, 11, 18-25.

consideration today.

Interestingly, in the 2011 Report “Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity”, McKinsey Global Institute specialists presented the definition of Big Data. As a data set whose size exceeds the capabilities of using traditional database software tools for their collection, storage, management and analysis, however, such a definition is subjective and emphasizes the size of data that could fit under Big Data⁵. Others define Big Data as a set of technologies that perform several operations: processing large data volumes than in the traditional sense, working with continuously incoming, structured or unstructured data in parallel in different aspects⁶. Still others point to the complex nature of Big Data, which includes both the data itself and the set of technologies associated with the processing of this data⁷. Summarizing the many opinions regarding the essence of Big Data, we can distinguish three approaches to its definition: 1) as information, 2) as a technology, or 3) as a complex institution that includes both the information itself and the technology for its processing. We are considering these approaches in more detail.

The first approach is based on the concept that Big Data is a technology. It is worth noting that the world practice refuses to define Big Data as a technology, indicating under this term only the object of analysis, that is, the data itself, which is more logical. The arguments refuting the expediency of considering Big Data as a technology might be given as follows.

The first and most obvious argument is the very name of the phenomenon – “Big Data”, which clearly describes its essence. At the same time, according to the Interstate Standards for Automated Systems, information technologies include “techniques, methods and methods of using computer technology in the

⁵ Manyika, J., Chui, M., Brown, B., Bughin, J., Dobbs, R., Roxburgh, C., & Hung Byers, A. (2011). Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity. McKinsey Global Institute.

⁶ Sagioglu, S., & Sinanc, D. (2013, May). Big data: A review. In *2013 international conference on collaboration technologies and systems (CTS)* (pp. 42-47). IEEE.

⁷ Davenport, Thomas H., Paul Barth, and Randy Bean. "How big data is different." (2012): 43-46.

performance of the functions of collecting, storing, processing, transmitting and using data”⁸.

A similar definition can be found in legislation of many developed countries “On Information, Information Technologies and Information Protection” where the legislator means “processes, methods of searching, collecting, storing, processing, providing, disseminating information and methods for implementing such processes”⁹ by information technologies and methods. Second, the features inherent in any technology do not coincide with the content of Big Data, among which, among others:

1. the existence of algorithmic processes and the possibility of their control;
2. the presence of an internal operational structure;
3. use of specific methods and mechanisms in technological processes;
4. the presence of a goal and a focus on achieving it.

Third, in the world of information technology, there are well-established terms that just define data processing technologies, that is, the very process of its analysis and structuring, such as “data mining”, “machine learning” (artificial intelligence, aimed at developing self-learning programs), “deep learning” (a type of machine learning that creates more complex and independent learning programs). Hence, we believe that the essence of technology does not correspond to the nature of Big Data, but is precisely a tool for processing them and obtaining a certain result. In our assumptions, it would be more correct to use the term “Big Data analytics” when we talk about technologies and processes for using Big Data (collection, storage, processing, use of results, etc.).

The second approach comes from the fact that Big Data is a bulk data array. For Big Data, there are traditional signs that most successfully, in our opinion, determine the essence of the content of the phenomenon under consideration

⁸ Phillips, F. (2017). A perspective on ‘Big Data’. *Science and Public Policy*, 44(5), 730-737.

⁹ Pejić Bach, M., Bertonecel, T., Meško, M., Suša Vugec, D., & Ivančić, L. (2020). Big data usage in European countries: Cluster analysis approach. *Data*, 5(1), 25.

within the framework of this approach. The first author who presented signs of a developing phenomenon was the American analyst Douglas B. Laney in 2001. In his article, he identified three main features that can characterize Big Data: 1) a large volume (Volume), 2) heterogeneity (Variety) and 3) conversion speed (Velocity). Collectively, they were called “three V “(3Vs)¹⁰. Later, as it developed, specialists identified additional features that may be inherent in Big Data, in particular, data value (Value) and data reliability (Veracity). We look at these features in more detail.

The features of Big Data

1. The first feature - a large volume (Volume) ¹¹, comes from the very concept of "Big Data". The information flow in the virtual space is growing exponentially. With the advent of the Internet, those processes of social life that previously existed in the real world began to flow into the online environment, which made them more accessible and efficient. Buying goods, communicating in social networks, the activities of enterprises and organizations in various fields - all these operations leave an information trail, creating a huge array of digital information. The continuous growth in the number of data collection sources, as well as the increase in the volume of data warehouses, determine the emergence of Big Data.

2. The second feature - data heterogeneity (Variety) ¹², follows from the first and consists in the diversity of data. As mentioned above, since the number of processes performed in the online environment is growing every year, the

¹⁰ Laney, D. (2001). 3-D data management: Controlling data volume, velocity and variety. Application Delivery Strategies by META Group Inc. *disponibile sul sito, available at: <https://blogs.gartner.com/doug-laney/files/2012/01/ad949-3D-Data-Management-Controlling-Data-Volume-Velocity-and-Variety.pdf>* (February 2001). URL: <https://blogs.gartner.com/doug-laney/files/2012/01/ad949-3D-Data-Management-Controlling-Data-Volume-Velocity-and-Variety.pdf>

¹¹ Katal, A., Wazid, M., & Goudar, R. H. (2013, August). Big data: issues, challenges, tools and good practices. In *2013 Sixth international conference on contemporary computing (IC3)* (pp. 404-409). IEEE.

¹² Auer, S., Scerri, S., Versteden, A., Pauwels, E., Charalambidis, A., Konstantopoulos, S., ... & Vidal, M. E. (2017). The BigDataEurope platform—supporting the variety dimension of big data. In *Web Engineering: 17th International Conference, ICWE 2017, Rome, Italy, June 5-8, 2017, Proceedings 17* (pp. 41-59). Springer International Publishing.

volume of information is also increasing. However, each perfect process can contain many types of data that are collected into a single unstructured mass of information. For instance, any social network contains all the personal information about a person that whoever wishes to provide. What's more, a single enterprise can contain thousands of different pieces of information, ranging from employee information to industrial data. The complexity of systematization and further processing of such data by traditional (“manual”) methods lies in the heterogeneity of their semantics, incompatibility of formats during collection, limited storage resources, and much more. Nevertheless, speaking of Big Data, one cannot limit oneself to the presence of only heterogeneous data. The incoming information can often be quite systematized, uniform in nature, which does not require large capacities for its structuring, but has a large volume. Due to the heterogeneity of Big Data, they should be divided into three large groups:

i) Custom big data. This category of data is created directly by the person himself in the process of using various platforms on the Internet, as well as other means that record human behavior (relocation data, data from social networks, video files, etc.).

ii) Industrial big data. Information of this type, as a rule, is generated not by a person, but by various technologies used in industry and other industries (sensors and sensors in an enterprise, video recorders, etc.)

iii) Anonymous big data. This category includes a set of data that does not contain personal identifiers of the subject, using which it is impossible to identify a specific individual without additional information.

3. The third feature - the speed of transformation (Velocity)¹³, is a consequence of the two previous ones and consists in the high speed of creating and modifying data. Taking into account a large amount of uniform or heterogeneous information, the situation is aggravated by its constant updating,

¹³ Chardonens, T., Cudre-Mauroux, P., Grund, M., & Perroud, B. (2013, October). Big data analytics on high Velocity streams: A case study. In *2013 IEEE International Conference on Big Data* (pp. 784-787). IEEE.

which traditional database analysis approaches do not manage to cope with all at once.

4. The fourth feature - value (Value)¹⁴, consists in the fact that not only the collected data in a raw, "raw" form, but also the result obtained after their processing have value. That is, by connecting at first glance "incompatible" data sets, analysts can get a completely unpredictable result for themselves. In view of this, for most organizations, the true benefit of having data appears after it has been systematized and obtained the necessary results, combining heterogeneous data. Many authors note "the true value of data is like an iceberg in the ocean. At first glance, only a small part of them is visible, while everything else is hidden under water".

5. The fifth feature is reliability (Veracity)¹⁵. As mentioned above, after processing information, it receives a certain value. Thinking deeply, it should be said that the value of the processed information also lies in the reliability of the data received. This raises the question of how reliable the sources from which the data were obtained, and subsequently, how true the results generated from such data will be. In addition, this feature is closely related to the aforementioned "Velocity" feature, since Big Data volatility is often uncontrollable, which leads to a natural loss of actualization and, accordingly, data reliability. The loss of a potentially necessary result can be considered a consequence of the unreliability of the data.

Conclusion

The paper can be concluded that the vast majority of information related to Big Data is of a secondary nature. In other words, while initially creating such data, their purpose is other than their reuse to perform analytical tasks. A similar

¹⁴ Günther, W. A., Mehrizi, M. H. R., Huysman, M., & Feldberg, F. (2017). Debating big data: A literature review on realizing value from big data. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 26(3), 191-209.

¹⁵ Rubin, V., & Lukoianova, T. (2013). Veracity roadmap: Is big data objective, truthful and credible?. *Advances in Classification Research Online*, 24(1), 4.

idea was reflected in the report of the American company AAPOR. Sociologist Sean Taylor referred to such data as “received” (the opposite of them – “created”) data¹⁶. An illustration for a better understanding could be data from social networks, whose users leave information for personal purposes, and not for the purpose of their further use, for example, by retailers to determine the needs of their customers.

Hence, analyzing the presented approach, we can conclude that Big Data should be considered precisely as a large amount of constantly changing heterogeneous information, which in turn makes us take a different look at the existing “world of data” and discover new information realities.

The final approach considers Big Data as a complex institution. Complexity lies in the combination of elements of information and technology. Recalling that the consideration of Big Data in the form of technology, in our opinion, is not entirely correct. Consequently, one can doubt the validity of the first part of this approach. It seems that such a way of interpreting the phenomenon under study, if it takes place, should be used for a broad description of the entire set of institutions associated with Big Data and differentiated with respect to the functions performed by Big Data. It is likely to be more useful for the technological field of activity, than for legal science; otherwise, the essential boundaries of this concept would be blurred. Meanwhile, for legislative practice, it seems more appropriate to confine ourselves to a narrow approach to Big Data, i.e. definition through the category of information and establish a special legal regulation of the new phenomenon. Based on the foregoing, we consider it appropriate to attribute Big Data to a type of information, because the features of Big Data indicate their informational nature. We suggest that Big Data must be understood as a dynamically changing huge set of structured or unstructured data, the value of

¹⁶ Japoc, L., Kreuter, F., Berg, M., Biemer, P., Decker, P., Lampe, C., Lane, J., O’Neil, C., Usher, A. AAPOR Report on big data: AAPOR big data task force. 2015. P. 18. URL: http://doku.iab.de/grauepap/2015/BigDataTaskForceReport_FINAL_2_12_15.pdf

which lies in obtaining new, reliable information by arranging them using intelligent methods of data analysis.

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